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IMPLEMENTATION OF SAFE SPACE USING SMART CITY TECHNOLOGIES IN UKRAINE

Smart City technology involves the use of information and communication technologies to improve the quality of life in urban areas, efficient resource management, cost reduction and sustainability. One of the areas of Smart City development is security. The main goal of a true smart city is to improve the quality of life of local residents. This means ensuring economic, social and environmental sustainability. [1]

At the moment, who better than Ukrainians to understand the importance of introducing a safer living space? The introduction of Smart City technology in Ukrainian cities began in 2015. There have been many projects to promote this technology, including in the context of security. For example, Kyiv Smart City, SMART CITY HUB, etc.

Smart cities can use various technologies to create safer spaces. A variety of technologies are used to do this. These include reducing crime, improving traffic, protecting the environment and improving public safety. [1] The following options are offered in the SMART CITY technology to improve the area of security against crime:

- use of surveillance cameras in strategic locations;
- analysis of crime data, which can help city authorities identify the places and times when crimes are most likely to occur and direct resources to prevent them;
- bright and uniform lighting of streets, parks and other public places;
- city authorities and public services can use mobile applications and other technologies to warn residents of dangerous situations, such as fires, natural disasters or terrorist attacks.

The following measures have been proposed to improve the situation in the field of traffic, which is a very important part of public safety:

- intelligent transport systems that can be used to optimise traffic lights, improve public transport coordination and provide traffic information to drivers;
- automatic control systems;
- pedestrian crossings with motion sensors and lighting;
- expansion of bicycle lanes and traffic lanes can make cycling safer.

It is generally accepted that a smart city is not only about innovation and technology, but also about environmental protection. We cannot but agree that all life depends on the state of the environment. That is why we should think about spreading the following environmental ideas:

- - sensors for monitoring air quality, water levels and other environmental factors;
- - smart meters, energy-efficient appliances and other technologies to reduce energy consumption;
- - smart bins and other technologies can help reduce pollution and improve waste management.

And the common factor for all of the above is the improvement of public safety. For distribution

- Smart cities can use technology to improve coordination between different emergency services, such as police, fire and ambulance services.
- Security cameras, motion sensors and other technologies can be used to detect and prevent terrorist attacks and other crimes.
- The city can use mobile apps and other technologies to warn residents of dangerous situations such as fires, natural disasters, or terrorist attacks.

"Kyiv Smart City is a programme aimed at transforming Kyiv into one of the most modern and safe cities in the world. The programme introduces various smart city technologies, such as smart street lights, smart car parks and smart garbage bins. These technologies help improve the quality of life of Kyiv residents and make the city safer. [2]

In 2024, UAH 32.4 million will be allocated from the Mykolaiv budget for the installation of video surveillance cameras under the Safe City programme.[3]

List of references:

1. SMART CITY Ukraine: what it is and how it works in Ukrainian realities. URL: <https://visitukraine.today/uk/blog/2183/smart-city-ukraine-what-it-is-and-how-it-works-in-ukrainian-realities> (accessed 20.05.2024).
2. The programme of the Kyiv Smart City Forum 2020 has been announced. URL: <https://kyiv24.news/news/stala-vidoma-programa-kyiv-smart-city-forum-2020> (accessed 20.05.2024).
3. Volyn news. Smart city technologies are being introduced in Lutsk. URL: <https://topnews.volyn.ua/society/2024/03/20/96583.html> (accessed 20.05.2024).